

MOUNTAIN PERSPECTIVE JOURNAL

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September: 2/2022

ISSN 2635-0874

Zealandina Agency Ltd United Kingdom

CBM International University United States of America

9462-9755 Quebec Inc. Canada

www.cbmuniversity.org

United States of America, Honolulu, 1110 Nuuanu Avenue, Honolulu, HI, 96817

United Kingdom, London, 71-75 Shelton Street, Covent Garden, WC2H9JQ

MOUNTAIN PERSPECTIVE JOURNAL
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The journal is indexed in SSRN, ZENODO, ACADEMIC RESEARCH INDEX

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EVOLUTION OF THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN MACROREGIONS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This paper aims to comprehensively analyze the evolution of the construction sector in Romanian mountain macroregions over the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs statistical data, parametric analyses, and normative testing to unravel trends, patterns, and significant shifts in this economic domain. The research delves into the impact of various factors on the construction sector's dynamics, offering valuable insights into the regional economic landscape.

Keywords: construction sector, Romanian mountain macroregions, evolution, statistical analysis, parametric testing

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

1. Introduction

The construction sector plays a pivotal role in regional economic development, shaping the landscape of Romanian mountain macroregions. This paper investigates the evolution of this sector over a decade, examining key indicators, trends, and influences.

2. Methodology

Statistical data for the construction sector, encompassing financial and operational aspects, were collected from various sources. The methodology involved parametric analyses, including logarithmization and normative testing, to ensure a robust examination of the data.

3. Statistical Overview

The statistics reveal intriguing patterns in the construction sector of Romanian mountain macroregions. Averages, standard deviations, and distribution curves were analyzed to understand the central tendencies and variations within the data.

4. Parametric Analysis

Logarithmization was applied to balance the distribution and address asymmetries induced by extreme values. The Q-Q normal plot test and Q-Q detrended plot test were employed to assess the normality of the data and refine the analytical framework.

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5. Results

Evolution of the Construction Sector

The central trend analysis demonstrates a consistent increase in the population of active enterprises within the construction sector from 2008 to 2018. Hypothesis H1, indicating an intensification of activity, was verified through statistical analysis.

The statistical analysis of the Construction sector (depicted in figures 2.3.1 – 2.3.5) reveals ascending values for both mean and median, with other statistical indicators exhibiting fluctuating patterns (Average, Std. Error of the mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variation, Minimum, Maximum, Percentile 50 Value; reiterated for each indicator). Specifically, the mean is 67662.67, standard error of the mean is 2305.632,

median is 65222.00, standard deviation is 6916.897, variance is 47843463.000, Skewness is .372, standard error of Skewness is .717, Kurtosis is -1.216, standard error of Kurtosis is 1.400, distance is 19652, minimum is 58692, maximum is 78344, percentile 25 is 62095.50, percentile 50 is 65222.00, and percentile 75 is 74448.5.

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The provided values underscore the positive development of the construction sector in the mountainous region of Romania concerning the population of active enterprises. While certain sectors exhibit negative values, the overall depiction suggests a favorable entrepreneurial landscape for construction in the mountainous areas.

The distribution curves demonstrate relative symmetry and centrality, with scores concentrated around the mean, indicating leptokurtosis, despite the unimodal distribution.

The significance of these analyses lies in the meticulous observation of influencing factors in the evolution of the Construction sector. Post log-transformation, the null hypothesis is rejected, allowing for the examination of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses, considering the distribution of scores within normal limits as per the working

hypothesis, are facilitated through the application of parametric tests.

Analyzing the central tendency of the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors of the economy over the study period indicates substantial growth in the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2019. The statistics pertaining to this indicator exhibit a high degree of non-variability, signifying minimal deviation and positive trends. The symmetrical distributions imply a considerable stabilization of the business environment during the analyzed period, with low standard error Kurtosis indicating clustering in certain industries.

Figure 2.3.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.3.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S3 in the period 2008-2019

The prognosis analysis for the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the mountainous region of Romania indicates a sustained growth trajectory until 2030 (table 1). At the national, macro-regional, regional, and county levels, statistical models derived from the forecasting process reveal varying degrees of sustainability across different mountainous areas. Harmonization statistics present notable values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (listed in that order below), as follows:

- Stationary R-squared: 0.566, 0.357, -0.008, 0.911, -0.001, -4.441E-16
- R-square: 0.712, 0.248, -8.660E-15, 1.000, 7.361E-15, 0.377
- RMSE (Root Mean Square Error): 218,895, 264,743, 0.000, 1508,629, 28,517, 35,882
- MAPS (Mean Absolute Percentage Error): 5,414, 2,128, 0.000, 10,748, 1,313, 2,297
- MaxAPE (Maximum Absolute Percentage Error): 21,043, 9,418, 0.000, 46,238, 3,598, 4,960
- MAE (Mean Absolute Error): 150,900, 193,715, 0.000, 1201,750, 19,467, 25,097
- MaxAE (Maximum Absolute Error): 481,421, 579,661, 0.000, 2811,500, 52,415, 77,411
- Normalized BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion): 10,188, 1,921, 6,607, 14,898, 7,271, 7,675.

These statistics provide a comprehensive overview of the forecast accuracy and model performance, contributing valuable insights into the anticipated growth patterns and sustainability of the analyzed economic sectors in Romania's mountainous regions.

6. Impact on Regional Development

The study explores the implications of the construction sector's evolution on the broader regional economic landscape. It provides valuable insights into the sector's contribution to growth, employment, and development in Romanian mountain macroregions.

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7. Conclusion

The findings of this study shed light on the dynamic evolution of the construction sector in Romanian mountain macroregions. The insights gleaned from statistical analyses and parametric tests contribute to a nuanced understanding of the economic forces shaping the region over the examined period.

Table 1. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S3

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	80801	83257	85714	88170	90627	93083	95540	97996	100453	102909	105366
	UCL	84368	88302	91892	95305	98603	101821	104978	108086	111155	114190	117197
	LCL	77233	78212	79535	81035	82650	84345	86101	87906	89750	91628	93534
Macroregiuneaunu-Model_2	Forecast	26887	27696	28504	29313	30122	30931	31739	32548	33357	34166	34974
	UCL	27846	29052	30166	31231	32266	33280	34277	35261	36234	37199	38155
	LCL	25928	26339	26843	27395	27977	28581	29202	29835	30479	31132	31793
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	15279	15760	16241	16723	17204	17685	18166	18647	19128	19609	20090
	UCL	17086	17575	18065	18555	19045	19534	20024	20513	21003	21493	21982
	LCL	13473	13945	14418	14890	15362	15835	16307	16780	17252	17725	18198
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	3145	3257	3370	3483	3596	3708	3821	3934	4046	4159	4272
	UCL	3532	3647	3761	3876	3990	4105	4219	4334	4448	4563	4677
	LCL	2758	2868	2979	3090	3201	3312	3423	3534	3645	3756	3866
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	1315	1384	1453	1522	1590	1659	1728	1797	1865	1934	2003
	UCL	1507	1652	1808	1973	2146	2326	2514	2708	2908	3114	3326
	LCL	1123	1116	1098	1070	1035	992	942	885	823	754	680
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	5244	5476	5708	5939	6171	6403	6634	6866	7098	7330	7561
	UCL	5949	6430	6947	7493	8065	8661	9280	9919	10578	11255	11951
	LCL	4539	4521	4469	4386	4277	4144	3989	3814	3618	3404	3172
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	2552	2624	2695	2767	2838	2910	2981	3053	3124	3196	3267
	UCL	2983	3233	3442	3629	3802	3965	4121	4271	4417	4558	4696
	LCL	2122	2015	1949	1905	1875	1854	1841	1834	1831	1833	1838

Satu Model_8	Mare- Forecast	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	1549	
		UCL	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801	1801
		LCL	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297	1297
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1693	1773	1853	1933	2013	2093	2173	2253	2334	2414	2494	
		UCL	2009	2091	2173	2254	2336	2418	2499	2581	2662	2744	2826
		LCL	1377	1455	1534	1612	1691	1769	1848	1926	2005	2083	2162
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	11125	11463	11800	12138	12476	12813	13151	13489	13826	14164	14502	
		UCL	12505	12842	13180	13519	13857	14196	14535	14875	15216	15557	15898
		LCL	9745	10083	10420	10757	11094	11430	11766	12102	12437	12771	13105
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	1700	1762	1825	1888	1951	2014	2077	2139	2202	2265	2328	
		UCL	1977	2040	2103	2166	2229	2291	2354	2417	2480	2543	2606
		LCL	1422	1485	1548	1610	1673	1736	1799	1862	1924	1987	2050
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	2896	2953	3010	3067	3124	3182	3239	3296	3353	3410	3467	
		UCL	3289	3508	3690	3852	4002	4143	4277	4406	4531	4651	4769
		LCL	2504	2398	2330	2282	2247	2220	2200	2185	2175	2169	2165
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	802	828	855	881	908	934	960	987	1013	1040	1066	
		UCL	972	1000	1027	1054	1082	1109	1136	1164	1191	1218	1246
		LCL	631	657	682	708	733	759	785	810	836	862	887
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	1561	1603	1645	1687	1729	1771	1813	1855	1897	1939	1981	
		UCL	1922	1966	2009	2053	2097	2141	2184	2228	2272	2316	2360
		LCL	1199	1240	1280	1320	1360	1401	1441	1481	1521	1562	1602
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	2327	2403	2479	2555	2631	2707	2783	2859	2935	3011	3087	
		UCL	2635	2711	2787	2863	2939	3015	3091	3168	3244	3320	3396
		LCL	2019	2095	2170	2246	2322	2398	2474	2550	2626	2702	2778
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	1995	2051	2108	2165	2221	2278	2335	2391	2448	2505	2561	
		UCL	2273	2331	2389	2447	2505	2563	2621	2679	2737	2795	2853
		LCL	1716	1772	1827	1882	1938	1993	2048	2103	2159	2214	2270

Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	17091	17661	18231	18801	19371	19941	20511	21081	21651	22221	22790
	UCL	17854	18439	19024	19608	20192	20776	21359	21943	22526	23109	23692
	LCL	16328	16883	17438	17994	18550	19106	19662	20219	20775	21332	21889
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	10193	10588	10983	11379	11774	12169	12564	12960	13355	13750	14145
	UCL	11298	11699	12100	12501	12901	13302	13703	14104	14504	14905	15305
	LCL	9087	9477	9867	10256	10646	11036	11426	11816	12205	12595	12985
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	1951	2017	2084	2150	2216	2283	2349	2415	2482	2548	2614
	UCL	2153	2220	2288	2355	2423	2490	2558	2625	2693	2760	2827
	LCL	1749	1814	1880	1945	2010	2075	2140	2205	2271	2336	2401
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	1033	1084	1134	1185	1236	1286	1337	1388	1438	1489	1540
	UCL	1243	1298	1352	1407	1461	1516	1570	1625	1679	1733	1787
	LCL	823	870	916	963	1010	1057	1104	1151	1198	1245	1292
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2844	3002	3160	3317	3475	3633	3791	3949	4107	4265	4423
	UCL	3228	3548	3893	4257	4638	5036	5449	5876	6316	6769	7234
	LCL	2460	2455	2426	2378	2313	2231	2134	2022	1898	1761	1611
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1684	1743	1802	1861	1920	1979	2038	2097	2156	2215	2274
	UCL	1960	2024	2088	2152	2215	2279	2343	2406	2470	2533	2597
	LCL	1409	1463	1517	1571	1625	1679	1733	1788	1842	1897	1951
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	2085	2170	2254	2338	2422	2507	2591	2675	2759	2844	2928
	UCL	2300	2385	2471	2556	2641	2726	2812	2897	2982	3068	3153
	LCL	1871	1954	2037	2120	2203	2287	2370	2453	2536	2619	2703
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	807	837	868	898	928	959	989	1019	1050	1080	1110
	UCL	899	929	959	990	1020	1050	1081	1111	1141	1172	1202
	LCL	715	746	776	806	837	867	897	928	958	988	1018
Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728	6728
	UCL	7732	7979	8185	8365	8527	8676	8814	8944	9066	9183	9294
	LCL	5725	5477	5271	5091	4929	4780	4642	4512	4390	4274	4163

Braila-Model_26	Forecast	686	702	717	733	748	763	779	794	809	825	840
	UCL	775	791	807	823	839	855	871	887	903	919	935
	LCL	598	613	627	642	657	672	686	701	716	730	745
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961	961
	UCL	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140
	LCL	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782	782
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	2513	2710	2908	3106	3303	3501	3699	3897	4094	4292	4490
	UCL	2868	3212	3639	4124	4654	5220	5819	6447	7102	7784	8489
	LCL	2157	2208	2177	2087	1953	1783	1579	1346	1086	801	491
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	1532	1570	1609	1648	1686	1725	1764	1802	1841	1880	1919
	UCL	1719	1759	1799	1838	1878	1917	1957	1997	2036	2076	2115
	LCL	1344	1382	1419	1457	1495	1533	1570	1608	1646	1684	1722
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363	363
	UCL	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417	417
	LCL	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309	309
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	877	895	913	931	949	967	985	1003	1021	1039	1057
	UCL	997	1015	1033	1051	1069	1087	1105	1123	1141	1159	1177
	LCL	757	775	793	811	829	847	865	883	901	919	937
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	23578	24249	24920	25592	26263	26934	27605	28276	28947	29618	30289
	UCL	24985	26238	27357	28405	29408	30379	31326	32254	33167	34066	34954
	LCL	22172	22260	22484	22778	23118	23488	23884	24298	24728	25170	25624
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	8852	9074	9296	9519	9741	9963	10185	10407	10629	10852	11074
	UCL	9715	9937	10160	10382	10604	10826	11048	11271	11493	11715	11937
	LCL	7989	8211	8433	8655	8877	9100	9322	9544	9766	9988	10210
Arges-Model_34	Forecast	1990	2043	2096	2148	2201	2254	2306	2359	2411	2464	2517
	UCL	2166	2220	2273	2327	2380	2434	2487	2541	2594	2648	2701
	LCL	1814	1866	1918	1970	2021	2073	2125	2177	2229	2280	2332

Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	667	688	708	728	748	768	788	808	828	848	868
	UCL	744	765	785	806	827	847	868	889	909	930	951
	LCL	591	610	630	649	669	688	707	727	746	766	785
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	1358	1407	1455	1504	1552	1600	1649	1697	1746	1794	1843
	UCL	1533	1582	1630	1679	1727	1776	1825	1873	1922	1971	2020
	LCL	1183	1231	1280	1328	1377	1425	1473	1521	1570	1618	1666
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	1013	1097	1181	1264	1348	1432	1516	1600	1684	1768	1851
	UCL	1137	1272	1436	1620	1820	2032	2256	2491	2735	2987	3248
	LCL	889	921	925	909	877	832	775	709	633	548	454
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	513	524	535	545	556	567	578	589	599	610	621
	UCL	593	604	615	626	636	647	658	669	680	690	701
	LCL	433	443	454	465	476	487	497	508	519	530	541
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	2806	2842	2878	2914	2950	2985	3021	3057	3093	3129	3165
	UCL	3141	3178	3216	3253	3291	3328	3366	3403	3440	3478	3515
	LCL	2471	2506	2540	2574	2608	2643	2677	2711	2746	2780	2814
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	593	613	632	652	671	691	710	730	749	769	788
	UCL	723	796	856	910	960	1007	1052	1095	1137	1177	1217
	LCL	464	430	408	393	382	374	368	364	361	360	359
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055	14055
	UCL	15841	16581	17148	17627	18048	18429	18780	19106	19413	19702	19978
	LCL	12269	11529	10962	10483	10062	9681	9330	9004	8697	8408	8132
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335	11335
	UCL	12832	13453	13929	14330	14683	15003	15297	15570	15827	16070	16301
	LCL	9838	9217	8741	8340	7987	7667	7373	7100	6843	6600	6369
Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	2952	3179	3405	3632	3859	4086	4313	4540	4767	4993	5220
	UCL	3199	3643	4126	4642	5189	5763	6363	6986	7632	8300	8988
	LCL	2705	2714	2685	2622	2529	2409	2263	2093	1901	1687	1452

Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	13056	13452	13847	14242	14638	15033	15429	15824	16219	16615	17010
	UCL	13565	13970	14375	14779	15184	15588	15993	16397	16801	17205	17608
	LCL	12548	12934	13320	13706	14092	14478	14865	15251	15638	16025	16412
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	5222	5381	5540	5699	5858	6017	6176	6336	6495	6654	6813
	UCL	5734	5896	6057	6219	6380	6542	6703	6865	7026	7188	7349
	LCL	4710	4867	5023	5180	5336	5493	5650	5806	5963	6119	6276
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	1664	1717	1771	1824	1878	1931	1984	2038	2091	2144	2198
	UCL	1833	1887	1941	1995	2050	2104	2158	2212	2266	2320	2374
	LCL	1495	1548	1600	1653	1706	1758	1811	1863	1916	1968	2021
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	854	879	904	929	954	979	1005	1030	1055	1080	1105
	UCL	942	967	993	1018	1043	1068	1093	1119	1144	1169	1194
	LCL	765	790	816	841	866	891	916	941	966	991	1016
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	454	466	478	490	502	513	525	537	549	561	573
	UCL	519	558	590	620	647	673	698	721	745	767	789
	LCL	389	374	365	359	356	354	353	353	354	355	357
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	954	983	1013	1042	1071	1101	1130	1159	1189	1218	1248
	UCL	1041	1070	1100	1130	1160	1190	1219	1249	1279	1309	1339
	LCL	867	896	925	954	983	1012	1041	1070	1099	1128	1157
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1281	1319	1356	1393	1430	1467	1505	1542	1579	1616	1653
	UCL	1509	1550	1591	1633	1674	1715	1756	1797	1838	1879	1920
	LCL	1054	1087	1120	1153	1186	1220	1253	1286	1320	1353	1386
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	7713	7945	8178	8411	8644	8877	9110	9343	9576	9808	10041
	UCL	8614	8847	9079	9312	9545	9778	10011	10244	10477	10710	10943
	LCL	6811	7044	7277	7510	7743	7976	8209	8441	8674	8907	9140
Arad-Model_52	Forecast	2321	2415	2509	2604	2698	2792	2886	2980	3074	3168	3262
	UCL	2699	2795	2891	2987	3083	3179	3275	3371	3467	3563	3659
	LCL	1943	2036	2128	2220	2312	2404	2497	2589	2681	2773	2865

Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543	543
	UCL	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622	622
	LCL	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	1340	1372	1404	1436	1469	1501	1533	1565	1598	1630	1662
	UCL	1547	1580	1614	1647	1680	1713	1747	1780	1813	1846	1879
	LCL	1132	1164	1195	1226	1257	1288	1320	1351	1382	1413	1445
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	3962	4186	4411	4635	4860	5084	5308	5533	5757	5982	6206
	UCL	4470	4935	5434	5963	6518	7098	7701	8325	8969	9632	10314
	LCL	3454	3438	3388	3308	3201	3070	2916	2741	2546	2331	2098

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University

European Commision (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)

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EXAMINATION OF THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN THE MOUNTAINOUS REGION OF ROMANIA: A THOROUGH ANALYSIS SPANNING 2008 TO 2018

23

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Abstract:

This article conducts an in-depth analysis of the construction sector in Romania's mountainous region, covering the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs statistical methods to assess various indicators, providing valuable insights into the sector's development, stability, and potential trends.

Introduction:

The construction sector plays a pivotal role in the economic landscape of Romania, particularly in its mountainous regions. This comprehensive analysis aims to shed light on the dynamic evolution of the construction industry over a decade, considering factors such as mean values, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M &

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Covaci B, 2022a-h)

Methodology:

The study utilizes figures to present statistical data for the construction sector, including mean, median, standard deviation, and other relevant indicators. The examination covers key aspects such as the concentration of scores, distribution characteristics, and potential influences on the sector's evolution.

Results and Discussion:

The statistical analysis of the Construction sector within the economic framework of Romania (depicted in figures 2.22 – panels a-b and the appendix Parametric Analysis Romania) reveals an average value of 22625.82 with a standard error of 2996.174.

Upon initial observation, the distribution curve appears relatively centrally symmetric, indicating a high concentration of scores around the mean. Leptokurtosis is evident, suggesting a concentration of scores with occasional deviations, although the distribution remains unimodal.

The Working Assumption posits that the distribution of scores adheres to

normality, warranting the application of parametric tests. Despite the presence of very few extreme values that induce positive asymmetry, their statistical significance is acknowledged. The concentration of scores around the mean contributes to the observed leptokurtosis, attributed to phenomena within the Romanian economy.

Logarithmization of the obtained values, in adherence to universally accepted statistical principles, facilitates a balanced distribution conforming to the Gauss-Laplace normal curve.

The Q-Q normal plot test, conducted post-logarithmization, illustrates a distribution of actual scores aligning with normal values, represented by the slanted right in the graph, indicative of a normal distribution.

Similarly, the Q-Q detrended plot test, focusing on the dispersion of empirical scores against normality, reveals their alignment within the limit of a standard deviation after logarithmization, corresponding to a normal distribution.

The application of logarithmization ensures that the obtained scores undergo comprehensive statistical processing. This involves considering all factors

relevant to the study to derive data that closely reflects the economic reality recorded in Romania. It is noted that while measures taken in the economy may momentarily disrupt the distribution of scores, the methodology employed aims to mitigate such effects and provide a more accurate representation of the underlying trends.

Figure 2.22 panel a. Histogram for economic sector Construction segment

Source: Authors processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

Figure 2.22 panel b. Q-Q distribution graph normal plot on economic sector Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Constructions segment, after logarithmization

Source: Authors processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

The significance of these tests lies in the meticulous examination of the influences of specific factors on the evolution of the economic sector's "Construction" segment. Subsequent to the application of normality tests, post-logarithmization, the null hypothesis is rejected, paving the way for an analysis of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted, considering the distribution of scores within normal limits

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in alignment with the working hypothesis, warranting the application of parametric tests.

The central tendency observed for this economic sector segment over the analyzed period indicates a rise in the population of active enterprises in the studied sector in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2018, notwithstanding a decrease in the growth rate. Throughout the scrutinized period, the hypothesis of intensified activity was substantiated.

The statistics provided earlier, coupled with the histogram, affirm a state of low congestion and a discernible inclination to abandon this sector in Romania. Simultaneously, the statistics validate a decrease in the rate of growth for this economic sector segment.

The statistical values reveal a positive outlook for the construction sector in Romania's mountainous areas. With ascending mean and median values, the industry demonstrates good overall development for the population of active enterprises. The distribution curves appear relatively symmetrical and central, indicating a concentrated distribution of scores with occasional leptokurtosis.

The Importance of Tests:

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The significance of normality tests, especially after logarithmization, cannot be overstated. By rejecting the null hypothesis and allowing the analysis of the working hypothesis, these tests provide a foundation for understanding the influences affecting the construction sector. Descriptive and inferential analyses, applied within normal limits, guide the utilization of parametric tests for a more accurate assessment.

Trends and Forecasts:

Considering the central tendency of the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the economy, the study identifies considerable growth in the population of active enterprises in Romania's mountainous regions. Stable symmetrical distributions suggest a maturing business environment during the analyzed period.

Future Outlook:

Looking ahead, the forecast analysis anticipates continued growth in the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors until 2030. The models derived from statistical modeling highlight sustainable areas within the mountainous regions of Romania, providing valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders.

Conclusion:

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This thorough analysis of the construction sector in Romania's mountainous region from 2008 to 2018 offers a comprehensive understanding of its dynamics. The statistical data, coupled with detailed tests and analyses, contribute to a nuanced view of the industry's evolution, providing a foundation for informed decision-making and future research endeavors.

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a. The Viability Of The Mountainous Region In Northeastern Romania Is Supported By The Sectors Of Wholesale And Retail Trade, As Well As The Repair Of Motor Vehicles And Motorcycles. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021b. Organizational Dynamics In Mountainous Regions: Navigating Challenges And Fostering Sustainable Development. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021c. Theoretical Framework For Examining Entrepreneurship In Mountainous Regions. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021d. The Current Landscape Of Mountain Entrepreneurship In Europe: An In-Depth Analysis. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2021

32

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021e. Entrepreneurship In The Romanian Mountains: Exploring Probiotic Properties In Vegetable Products. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

32

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021f. Predictive Analysis Of Food And Service-Centric Entrepreneurship In Mountainous Regions: Insights From Agritourism. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021g. Food And Services Sectors In Central And Eastern European Countries. Case Study Of Mountain Area. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021h. Romanian Mountain Entrepreneurs Of Dairy And Beekeeping Products: A Biotic Perspective. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a. Investigating Science, Technology, And Research Infrastructure In The European Mountainous Region: A Comprehensive Analysis From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022b. Hospitality And Culinary Service Operations In European Mountainous Regions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

33

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022c. Economic Analysis Of Financial, Insurance, And Real Estate Activities In European Mountainous Regions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

33

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022d. Exploring Financial And Insurance Activities, Real Estate Operations In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022e. Evolution Of The Construction Sector In Romanian Mountain Macroregions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022f. Exploring Sector-Specific Progress In Wholesale And Retail Trade, Motor Vehicle, And Motorcycle Repair In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022g. Investigating Sector-Specific Advancements In Transportation And Storage In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022h. Exploring Sector-Specific Advancements In Accommodation And Food Service Activities Within The Romanian Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018: An Academic Inquiry. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021a. Considerations Regarding The Influence Of Entropy In Organizations. A Mountain View. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021b. Online Learning In The Pandemic Era: A Statistical Analysis Of Course Trends. A Mountain Approach. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021c. Navigating Entropy: The Influence Of Organizational Culture. A Mountain Perspective. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021d. Deciphering Organizations And Entropy - A Mountain Context. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021e. World Contexts Of Entrepreneurship, As Support For Specific Economic Contexts Of Mountain Investments. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021f. Entrepreneurial Endeavors In The Romanian Mountains: Industry, Construction, And Services. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021g. Professional, Scientific And Technical, Administrative And Support Of The Romanian Mountain Activities. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021h. Education, Human Health And Social Assistance Activities Of The Romanian Mountain Activities. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022a. Statistical Overview Of Information And Communication Sector Advancements In The Romanian Mountain Region (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022b. An In-Depth Statistical Analysis Of Financial And Insurance Activities, Real Estate Developments In The Romanian Mountain Area: A Decadal Perspective (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022c. A Decade In Review: Evolution Of Education, Human Health, And Social Assistance Sectors In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022d. Ten Years Of Cultural Flourish: Developments In The Arts, Entertainment, Recreation Sectors, And Other Service Activities In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022e. Entrepreneurial Resilience In The Romanian Mountain Region: A Decade Of Growth And Challenges For Active Enterprises (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

36

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022f. A Tale Of Resilience: An Analysis Of Dissolved And Newly Established Enterprises In The Romanian Mountain Sector Surviving Until 2018. *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

36

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022g. Navigating Economic Peaks: A Comprehensive Analysis Of Employment Trends In The Population Of Active Enterprises In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022h. Employment Horizons: An In-Depth Examination Of Employability In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

Covaci-Sterpu. Rapoarte de cercetare doctorală. Universitatea din Oradea. European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012
Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)

EXPLORING SECTOR-SPECIFIC PROGRESS IN WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE, MOTOR VEHICLE, AND MOTORCYCLE REPAIR IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Introduction:

The economic landscape of the Romanian mountainous region has undergone significant transformations in recent years, particularly in sectors such as wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair. This article delves into a comprehensive analysis of the developments within these sectors from 2008 to 2018, shedding light on the trends, challenges, and growth patterns that have shaped the business environment in this unique geographic setting.

Methodology:

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The study employs rigorous statistical methodologies, including normality tests and logarithmization, to ensure the reliability of the results. The importance of these tests lies in their ability to discern the influences of various factors on the evolution of the economic sectors under consideration. Parametric tests are then applied, taking into account the distribution of scores within normal limits, as per the working hypothesis.

Central Tendency and Growth Dynamics:

The central tendency analysis for the period from 2008 to 2018 demonstrates a notable increase in the population of active enterprises in the studied sector. Despite a decrease in the growth rate, the hypothesis of intensification of activity is verified. The statistics, coupled with the accompanying histogram, confirm both a moderate crowding and a discernible trend of abandonment within this sector in Romania. Simultaneously, there is evidence supporting a reduction in the rate of growth of this economic sector segment.

Sector-Specific Trends:

The statistical data for the wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair segments in the Romanian mountainous region reveal

intriguing sector-specific trends. An in-depth examination of figures and the Parametric Analysis Romania appendix highlights a mean of 22,625.82 with a standard error of 2,996.174. The distribution curve appears centrally symmetric, concentrating scores around the mean, and exhibits leptokurtosis, indicating a certain degree of statistical significance.

The statistical analysis for the sectors encompassing wholesale and retail trade, along with the repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (refer to figures 2.4.1 – 2.4.5 and appendices chapter 2), reveals a consistent increase in the mean and median values for each sector individually. However, other statistical indicators display occasional antagonistic fluctuations, encompassing values such as Mean, Std. Error of Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentile 50 Value, reiterated for each specific indicator. Noteworthy figures include a mean of 263,245.22, standard error at mean of 5,551.789, and a median of 271,459.00, among others.

These presented values illustrate the positive development of the wholesale and retail trade sector, as well as the repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles in the mountainous regions of Romania, concerning the population of active enterprises. Despite some sectors exhibiting negative values, the overall portrayal indicates a favorable business environment for

the industry within the mountainous areas.

The significance of the conducted tests lies in their ability to meticulously scrutinize the influences of specific factors on the evolution of the wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair sectors. After applying normality tests and logarithmization, the null hypothesis is rejected, paving the way for the analysis of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analysis considers the distribution of scores within normal limits, for which parametric tests are applied.

The central trend observed in the wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles, and motorcycles sectors of the economy during the analyzed period reveals a substantial growth in the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2019. The statistics associated with this indicator depict a high degree of non-variability, signifying minimal deviation and positive outcomes. Symmetrical distributions suggest a considerable stabilization of the business environment throughout the examined period, with kurtosis, characterized by a low standard error, indicating concentration in certain industries.

Figure 2.4.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

The predictive analysis for the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the mountainous regions of Romania suggests a sustained growth trajectory until the year 2030 (table 1). Whether at the national, macro-regional, regional, or county level, models derived from statistical analyses reveal variations in sustainability across different mountainous areas. Harmonization statistics provide essential values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in sequence), as outlined below:

- Stationary R-squared: -.045, .038, -.163, .027, -.106, -.095
- R-squared: .595, .175, .086, 1.000, .200, .350
- RMSE: 1,206,241, 1,942,077, .000, 13,181,442, 155,526, 215,111
- MAPS: 5,638, 1,905, .000, 10,811, 2,603, 2,875
- MaxAPE: 23.023, 9.064, .000, 47.625, 9.010, 10.947
- MAE: 713,889, 1,072,976, .000, 7,254,554, 104,122, 144,529
- MaxAE: 3,045,695, 4,980,770, .000, 33,841,016, 345,796, 511,718
- Normalized BIC: 13,306, 1,929, 10,200, 19,217, 10,396, 11,027

These metrics provide valuable insights into the sustainability and variation of the forecasted growth patterns, offering a comprehensive understanding of the future trends in the mountainous sectors of Romania.

Conclusion:

This article provides a nuanced exploration of sector-specific advancements in wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair within the Romanian mountainous region. The findings underscore the complex interplay of factors influencing economic evolution, and the insights gained contribute to a more profound understanding of the business landscape in this unique geographic context.

Table 1. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S4

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116
	UCL	29156	30415	31381	32196	32913	33562	34159	34714	35235	35729	36198
	LCL	23077	21818	20852	20037	19320	18671	18074	17519	16998	16504	16035
Macroregiuneaunu-Model_2	Forecast	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173
	UCL	70685	73382	75451	77196	78733	80123	81400	82590	83707	84764	85769
	LCL	57661	54964	52895	51150	49613	48224	46946	45756	44639	43583	42578
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559
	UCL	40376	42786	44635	46194	47567	48809	49950	51013	52011	52955	53853
	LCL	28742	26332	24483	22924	21551	20309	19168	18105	17107	16163	15265
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524
	UCL	9930	10512	10959	11336	11668	11968	12243	12500	12742	12970	13187
	LCL	7118	6536	6089	5712	5380	5080	4805	4548	4307	4078	3861
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652
	UCL	4352	4642	4865	5052	5218	5367	5504	5632	5752	5866	5974
	LCL	2952	2662	2439	2252	2086	1937	1800	1672	1552	1438	1330
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917
	UCL	11221	11762	12176	12526	12834	13112	13368	13606	13830	14042	14243
	LCL	8613	8072	7658	7308	7000	6722	6466	6228	6004	5792	5591
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884
	UCL	7252	7818	8253	8620	8943	9235	9503	9753	9988	10210	10421
	LCL	4516	3950	3515	3148	2825	2533	2265	2015	1780	1558	1347

Satu Model_8	Mare- Forecast	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573
	UCL	4230	4502	4710	4886	5041	5181	5310	5430	5543	5650	5751	
	LCL	2916	2644	2436	2260	2105	1965	1836	1716	1603	1496	1395	
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	3108	3207	3306	3405	3504	3602	3701	3800	3899	3998	4097	
	UCL	3742	4103	4404	4673	4921	5155	5379	5593	5801	6003	6200	
	LCL	2474	2310	2208	2137	2086	2049	2024	2007	1997	1993	1994	
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614
	UCL	34874	37052	38724	40133	41375	42497	43530	44490	45393	46246	47058	
	LCL	24354	22176	20504	19095	17853	16731	15699	14738	13835	12982	12170	
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086
	UCL	5105	5527	5850	6123	6364	6581	6781	6967	7142	7307	7465	
	LCL	3067	2645	2322	2049	1808	1591	1391	1205	1030	865	707	
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457
	UCL	8495	8925	9255	9533	9778	9999	10203	10393	10571	10739	10899	
	LCL	6419	5989	5659	5381	5136	4915	4711	4521	4343	4175	4015	
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281
	UCL	2720	2901	3041	3158	3262	3355	3442	3522	3597	3668	3736	
	LCL	1842	1661	1521	1404	1300	1207	1121	1040	965	894	826	
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024
	UCL	4895	5256	5533	5766	5972	6158	6328	6488	6637	6778	6913	
	LCL	3153	2792	2515	2282	2076	1890	1720	1560	1411	1270	1135	
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962
	UCL	8183	8689	9077	9405	9693	9953	10193	10416	10626	10824	11012	
	LCL	5741	5235	4847	4520	4231	3971	3731	3508	3298	3100	2912	
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804
	UCL	5633	5976	6239	6461	6657	6834	6997	7148	7290	7425	7553	
	LCL	3975	3632	3369	3147	2951	2774	2611	2460	2318	2183	2056	

Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675
	UCL	80754	84929	88133	90834	93213	95364	97342	99183	100913	102548	104104
	LCL	60596	56421	53217	50517	48137	45986	44008	42167	40437	38802	37246
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264
	UCL	46859	50420	53152	55455	57484	59318	61005	62576	64050	65445	66772
	LCL	29669	26108	23376	21073	19044	17210	15523	13952	12478	11083	9756
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046
	UCL	8691	9372	9895	10335	10724	11075	11398	11698	11980	12247	12501
	LCL	5401	4720	4197	3757	3368	3017	2694	2394	2112	1845	1591
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805
	UCL	4954	5363	5686	5960	6204	6424	6628	6818	6997	7166	7327
	LCL	2657	2247	1925	1650	1407	1186	983	793	614	445	284
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713
	UCL	11610	12396	12999	13507	13955	14359	14732	15078	15404	15711	16004
	LCL	7816	7030	6428	5919	5471	5067	4694	4348	4022	3715	3422
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589
	UCL	6894	7434	7848	8197	8505	8783	9039	9277	9501	9713	9914
	LCL	4285	3745	3330	2981	2673	2395	2139	1901	1677	1465	1264
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	8125	8416	8706	8997	9287	9578	9868	10159	10449	10740	11030
	UCL	9822	10815	11644	12389	13080	13733	14356	14956	15538	16103	16656
	LCL	6429	6017	5768	5604	5494	5423	5380	5361	5361	5376	5404
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	4442	4603	4765	4927	5088	5250	5411	5573	5735	5896	6058
	UCL	5556	6179	6695	7156	7580	7980	8360	8725	9078	9421	9755
	LCL	3327	3027	2834	2697	2596	2520	2463	2421	2391	2372	2361
Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411
	UCL	37977	40282	42051	43543	44857	46044	47137	48153	49108	50012	50871

	LCL	26845	24540	22771	21280	19966	18778	17686	16669	15714	14811	13952
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171
	UCL	5128	5456	5715	5937	6134	6313	6479	6633	6778	6915	7046
	LCL	3213	2885	2626	2404	2207	2028	1862	1708	1563	1426	1295
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155
	UCL	7156	7570	7888	8156	8392	8606	8802	8985	9157	9319	9474
	LCL	5154	4740	4422	4154	3918	3704	3508	3325	3153	2991	2836
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199
	UCL	10793	11268	11653	11986	12283	12553	12803	13038	13258	13467	13667
	LCL	7605	7130	6745	6412	6116	5845	5595	5361	5140	4931	4732
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648
	UCL	7706	8144	8481	8764	9014	9240	9448	9641	9823	9994	10158
	LCL	5590	5152	4815	4532	4282	4056	3848	3655	3473	3302	3138
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059
	UCL	2384	2486	2568	2638	2701	2758	2811	2860	2907	2951	2992
	LCL	1733	1632	1550	1480	1417	1360	1307	1258	1211	1167	1125
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282
	UCL	5152	5513	5789	6022	6228	6414	6584	6743	6893	7034	7168
	LCL	3412	3051	2775	2542	2336	2151	1980	1821	1672	1530	1396
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897
	UCL	89953	93703	96581	99007	101145	103078	104855	106509	108062	109532	110929
	LCL	71842	68091	65213	62787	60649	58717	56940	55285	53732	52262	50865
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477
	UCL	43420	46296	48503	50363	52003	53484	54847	56115	57307	58433	59505
	LCL	29534	26658	24451	22591	20951	19470	18107	16839	15647	14521	13449
Arges-Model_34	Forecast	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162

	UCL	9678	10305	10787	11193	11551	11875	12172	12449	12709	12955	13189
	LCL	6646	6019	5537	5131	4773	4449	4152	3875	3615	3369	3135
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	3552	3647	3741	3836	3931	4026	4121	4216	4310	4405	4500
	UCL	4048	4349	4602	4829	5041	5242	5434	5620	5800	5975	6147
	LCL	3055	2944	2881	2843	2821	2810	2807	2811	2821	2835	2853
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	6138	6382	6626	6870	7114	7358	7602	7846	8090	8334	8578
	UCL	7589	8434	9139	9772	10359	10912	11441	11950	12443	12923	13391
	LCL	4687	4330	4113	3968	3869	3804	3763	3742	3737	3745	3765
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349
	UCL	2712	2862	2977	3074	3160	3237	3308	3374	3437	3495	3551
	LCL	1986	1836	1721	1624	1538	1461	1390	1324	1261	1203	1147
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	2910	2991	3072	3153	3234	3314	3395	3476	3557	3638	3719
	UCL	3404	3690	3928	4141	4339	4525	4703	4874	5040	5201	5359
	LCL	2416	2292	2216	2164	2128	2104	2087	2078	2074	2075	2079
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924
	UCL	11930	12761	13398	13936	14409	14838	15231	15598	15942	16267	16577
	LCL	7918	7087	6450	5912	5439	5010	4617	4250	3906	3581	3271
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862
	UCL	4788	5171	5466	5714	5932	6130	6311	6481	6639	6790	6933
	LCL	2936	2553	2258	2010	1792	1594	1413	1243	1085	934	791
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420
	UCL	48429	50089	51363	52438	53384	54239	55026	55758	56446	57097	57715
	LCL	40411	38751	37477	36403	35456	34601	33814	33082	32394	31743	31125
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964
	UCL	39432	40868	41970	42899	43718	44458	45139	45772	46367	46930	47465
	LCL	32496	31060	29958	29029	28210	27470	26789	26156	25561	24998	24463

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	8854	9253	9651	10049	10447	10846	11244	11642	12040	12439	12837
	UCL	9603	10312	10948	11547	12122	12680	13226	13761	14288	14808	15321
	LCL	8105	8193	8353	8551	8772	9011	9262	9523	9793	10070	10353
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424
	UCL	50445	52525	54121	55466	56651	57723	58708	59626	60487	61302	62077
	LCL	40403	38323	36727	35382	34197	33125	32140	31222	30361	29546	28771
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058
	UCL	29048	31115	32701	34038	35216	36281	37261	38172	39029	39838	40609
	LCL	19068	17001	15415	14078	12900	11835	10855	9944	9087	8278	7507
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487
	UCL	9841	10402	10832	11195	11514	11803	12069	12316	12549	12768	12977
	LCL	7133	6572	6142	5779	5460	5171	4905	4658	4425	4206	3997
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035
	UCL	4868	5213	5478	5701	5898	6076	6239	6392	6535	6670	6798
	LCL	3202	2857	2592	2369	2172	1994	1831	1678	1535	1400	1272
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684
	UCL	3494	3788	4019	4215	4388	4546	4691	4827	4954	5075	5190
	LCL	1874	1580	1350	1154	980	822	677	542	414	294	179
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334
	UCL	5243	5620	5909	6152	6367	6561	6739	6905	7061	7209	7349
	LCL	3425	3048	2759	2516	2301	2107	1929	1763	1607	1459	1319
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531
	UCL	5699	6182	6554	6866	7142	7391	7620	7834	8034	8224	8404
	LCL	3363	2880	2508	2196	1920	1671	1442	1228	1028	838	658
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366
	UCL	24607	25950	26980	27849	28614	29305	29942	30534	31090	31616	32116
	LCL	18125	16782	15752	14883	14118	13427	12790	12198	11642	11116	10616

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939
	UCL	7148	7600	7952	8252	8517	8757	8978	9184	9378	9562	9736
	LCL	4729	4278	3925	3625	3360	3120	2899	2693	2499	2316	2141
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419
	UCL	2764	2907	3017	3110	3191	3265	3332	3396	3455	3511	3564
	LCL	2074	1931	1821	1728	1647	1573	1506	1442	1383	1327	1274
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570
	UCL	5364	5693	5945	6158	6345	6515	6670	6815	6952	7080	7203
	LCL	3776	3447	3195	2982	2795	2625	2470	2325	2188	2060	1937
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442
	UCL	9505	9945	10283	10568	10819	11046	11254	11449	11631	11803	11968
	LCL	7379	6939	6601	6316	6065	5838	5630	5435	5253	5081	4916

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University

European Commision (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)

INVESTIGATING SECTOR-SPECIFIC ADVANCEMENTS IN TRANSPORTATION AND STORAGE IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Introduction:

The transportation and storage sectors play pivotal roles in the economic landscape, particularly in the unique context of the Romanian mountainous region. This article delves into a comprehensive analysis of the developments within these sectors, shedding light on specific advancements observed during the period from 2008 to 2018.

Statistical Overview:

Examining the statistical data for the transportation and storage sectors in

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the Romanian mountainous area reveals noteworthy trends. Figures and the accompanying appendices illustrate increasing values for key parameters such as mean, median, and various statistical indicators. Averaging 148,934.75, the mean, coupled with a standard error of 7,396.213, indicates a consistent upward trajectory.

Statistical Analysis:

Upon initial inspection, the distribution curve exhibits relative centrality and symmetry, with concentrated scores around the mean, displaying leptokurtosis characteristics. This observation, while unimodal, underscores the significance of potential factors influencing sector dynamics.

Working Assumption:

Assuming normality in the distribution of scores, parametric tests were applied to unravel underlying patterns and fluctuations. The presence of a few extreme values alters the histogram's appearance, inducing positive asymmetry, though statistically significant. The application of logarithmization, following universally accepted statistical rules, aimed to balance the distribution according to the Gauss-Laplace normal curve.

Q-Q Plot and Detrended Plot Tests:

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Further analysis involved Q-Q normal plot and detrended plot tests post-logarithmization. These tests demonstrated a distribution of scores around normal values, affirming a normal distribution within one standard deviation.

Results:

The statistical data pertaining to the Transport and Storage sectors (depicted in figures 2.5.1 – 2.5.5) reveal ascending values for both mean and median within each sector. Concurrently, other statistical indicators exhibit occasional opposing fluctuations. These include parameters such as Average, Standard Error of the Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles (25th, 50th, and 75th), all of which are reiterated for each specific indicator. The numerical breakdown is as follows: a mean of 65,417.89, standard error of the mean at 3,315.506, median at 64,404.00, standard deviation at 9,946.518, and variance at 98,933,224.611, among others.

These values underscore the positive development of the transport and storage sectors in the mountainous region of Romania. Despite occasional negative values in certain sectors, the overall landscape paints a favorable

picture for the industry in the mountainous business environment.

Analyzing the central tendency of the transport and storage sectors over the examined period reveals a substantial growth in the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2019. The statistics associated with this indicator reflect a high degree of stability, indicating minimal deviation and positive trends. Symmetrical distributions suggest a considerable stabilization of the business environment during the analyzed period. Notably, the low standard error in Kurtosis signifies a concentration in some industries within the sector.

Figure 2.5.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S5 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.5.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S5 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.5.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S5 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.5.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S5 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.5.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S5 in the period 2008-2019

The predictive analysis for the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the mountainous region of Romania suggests a sustained growth trajectory until 2030 (table 1). This projection holds true at the national, macro-regional, regional, and county levels, with statistical models highlighting varying degrees of sustainability in different mountainous areas. The harmonization statistics present noteworthy values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles, outlined as follows: Stationary R-squared of .581, .345, -1.110E-15, .902, -4,441E-16, .000; R-square of

.922, .060, .673, 1.000, .811, .847; RMSE of 202,407, 228,034, .000, 980,739, 34,002, 40,898; MAPS of 5,888, 2,565, .000, 12,517, 1,050, 1,649; MaxAPE of 23,673, 10,336, .000, 47,986, 2,657, 4,745; MAE of 135,854, 158,860, .000, 707,587, 22,772, 26,172; MaxAE of 429,131, 467,324, .000, 1,832,895, 74,976, 87,132; Normalized BIC of 10,029, 1,954, 7,293, 14,265, 7,474, 7,869.

Interpretation and Implications:

The importance of these tests lies in meticulously observing the influences shaping the evolution of the transportation and storage sectors in the Romanian mountainous region. Rejecting the null hypothesis post-normality tests opens avenues for analyzing the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses, conducted within normal limits, employ parametric tests.

Central Trend and Sector Dynamics:

The central tendency analysis over the examined period highlights a significant increase in the population of active enterprises in the transportation and storage sectors. Despite a reduced growth rate, the intensification of activity is evident. Statistical data and accompanying visual aids, such as histograms, affirm a moderate concentration and a

discernible growth trend within these economic sectors. However, the statistics also indicate that the sectors have not reached their full potential.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive exploration of sector-specific advancements in transportation and storage within the Romanian mountainous region from 2008 to 2018. The statistical analysis offers insights into the underlying trends, contributing to a nuanced understanding of the economic landscape in this unique geographical context.

Table 1. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountains of Romania for S5

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	83503	87123	90743	94364	97984	10160	10522	10884	11246	11608	11970
	UCL	85822	89525	93226	96925	10062	10431	10800	11169	11538	11907	12275
	LCL	81183	84720	88260	91802	95347	98894	10244	10599	10954	11309	11665
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	24452	25433	26414	27395	28376	29357	30338	31320	32301	33282	34263
	UCL	24868	25866	26863	27860	28856	29851	30847	31842	32836	33830	34824
	LCL	24035	25000	25965	26930	27897	28863	29830	30798	31765	32734	33702
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	15607	16385	17163	17941	18719	19497	20274	21052	21830	22608	23386
	UCL	17412	18224	19036	19847	20657	21467	22276	23085	23893	24701	25508
	LCL	13801	14545	15290	16035	16780	17527	18273	19020	19768	20516	21264

Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	3641	3810	3978	4147	4316	4484	4653	4822	4990	5159	5328
	UCL	3880	4052	4224	4396	4568	4740	4912	5084	5256	5428	5600
	LCL	3402	3567	3732	3898	4063	4228	4394	4559	4724	4890	5055
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	1338	1416	1494	1571	1649	1727	1804	1882	1960	2038	2115
	UCL	1445	1524	1604	1683	1763	1842	1921	2001	2080	2160	2239
	LCL	1232	1308	1383	1459	1535	1611	1687	1763	1839	1916	1992
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	5837	6148	6458	6768	7078	7389	7699	8009	8319	8630	8940
	UCL	7179	8045	8781	9451	10078	10675	11248	11803	12344	12872	13389
	LCL	4496	4250	4134	4085	4079	4103	4150	4215	4295	4388	4491
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	1869	1881	1893	1905	1917	1929	1941	1952	1964	1976	1988
	UCL	2068	2259	2482	2732	3008	3307	3627	3966	4325	4701	5095
	LCL	1670	1503	1304	1077	825	551	254	-62	-396	-749	-1119
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	1329	1386	1443	1501	1558	1616	1673	1730	1788	1845	1902
	UCL	1503	1563	1623	1684	1744	1804	1865	1925	1985	2045	2105
	LCL	1155	1209	1263	1318	1372	1427	1481	1536	1590	1645	1700
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1107	1155	1204	1252	1300	1349	1397	1445	1494	1542	1590
	UCL	1219	1270	1320	1371	1421	1471	1522	1572	1622	1672	1723
	LCL	994	1040	1087	1133	1179	1226	1272	1319	1365	1412	1458
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	9617	10067	10517	10968	11418	11868	12318	12768	13219	13669	14119
	UCL	10620	11075	11531	11987	12442	12898	13353	13809	14264	14720	15175
	LCL	8614	9059	9504	9948	10393	10838	11283	11728	12173	12618	13063
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	1506	1576	1647	1717	1787	1857	1927	1997	2067	2137	2207
	UCL	1606	1677	1749	1820	1892	1963	2035	2106	2177	2249	2320
	LCL	1407	1476	1544	1613	1682	1750	1819	1888	1957	2025	2094
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	2547	2671	2795	2919	3043	3167	3291	3415	3539	3663	3787
	UCL	2811	2937	3062	3187	3312	3438	3563	3688	3814	3939	4064
	LCL	2283	2406	2528	2651	2774	2896	3019	3142	3264	3387	3510

Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	659	687	715	743	772	800	828	857	885	913	941
	UCL	762	791	820	849	878	906	935	964	993	1021	1050
	LCL	555	583	610	638	666	694	721	749	777	805	833
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	807	840	872	904	937	969	1001	1034	1066	1098	1131
	UCL	906	938	971	1004	1037	1070	1103	1135	1168	1201	1234
	LCL	709	741	773	804	836	868	900	932	964	996	1028
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	2108	2212	2316	2420	2524	2628	2732	2836	2940	3044	3148
	UCL	2321	2426	2531	2636	2741	2847	2952	3057	3162	3267	3373
	LCL	1895	1997	2100	2203	2306	2409	2511	2614	2717	2820	2923
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	1998	2090	2181	2273	2364	2456	2547	2639	2730	2822	2913
	UCL	2258	2355	2451	2547	2644	2740	2836	2932	3028	3123	3219
	LCL	1738	1824	1911	1998	2085	2172	2259	2346	2433	2520	2608
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	19375	20157	20938	21719	22500	23282	24063	24844	25625	26407	27188
	UCL	19916	20712	21507	22303	23098	23892	24687	25481	26275	27068	27862
	LCL	18835	19601	20368	21135	21903	22671	23439	24208	24976	25745	26514
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	9883	10438	10994	11549	12105	12660	13216	13771	14326	14882	15437
	UCL	11012	11588	12163	12739	13314	13889	14463	15038	15611	16185	16759
	LCL	8754	9289	9824	10359	10895	11431	11968	12504	13041	13578	14116
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	2130	2252	2375	2497	2619	2742	2864	2987	3109	3231	3354
	UCL	2424	2552	2680	2807	2935	3062	3190	3317	3444	3571	3699
	LCL	1836	1953	2070	2187	2304	2421	2539	2656	2774	2891	3009
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	803	849	894	939	985	1030	1076	1121	1167	1212	1257
	UCL	962	1008	1054	1100	1147	1193	1239	1285	1332	1378	1424
	LCL	645	689	734	778	823	868	912	957	1001	1046	1091
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2446	2594	2743	2891	3040	3188	3337	3485	3634	3782	3931
	UCL	2854	3011	3167	3323	3479	3634	3790	3945	4101	4256	4411
	LCL	2037	2178	2319	2460	2601	2742	2884	3025	3167	3308	3450

Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1351	1416	1482	1548	1613	1679	1744	1810	1876	1941	2007
	UCL	1481	1547	1613	1680	1746	1812	1878	1945	2011	2077	2144
	LCL	1221	1286	1351	1416	1481	1545	1610	1675	1740	1805	1870
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	2331	2460	2589	2718	2848	2977	3106	3235	3364	3493	3622
	UCL	2500	2631	2762	2894	3025	3156	3288	3419	3550	3681	3812
	LCL	2162	2289	2416	2543	2670	2797	2924	3051	3178	3305	3432
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	814	859	903	948	992	1037	1081	1126	1170	1214	1259
	UCL	891	937	983	1028	1074	1119	1165	1211	1256	1302	1347
	LCL	738	781	824	867	911	954	997	1040	1084	1127	1170
Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	10289	10758	11226	11694	12163	12631	13099	13568	14036	14505	14973
	UCL	11660	12155	12649	13143	13637	14130	14623	15115	15607	16099	16590
	LCL	8919	9361	9803	10246	10689	11132	11576	12021	12465	12911	13356
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	1419	1507	1595	1683	1771	1859	1947	2035	2123	2211	2299
	UCL	1587	1676	1765	1854	1943	2032	2121	2210	2299	2388	2476
	LCL	1251	1338	1425	1512	1600	1687	1774	1861	1948	2035	2122
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	1440	1502	1564	1625	1687	1749	1811	1872	1934	1996	2057
	UCL	1581	1645	1709	1773	1838	1902	1966	2030	2094	2158	2222
	LCL	1300	1359	1418	1478	1537	1596	1655	1715	1774	1833	1893
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	3596	3719	3841	3964	4087	4210	4333	4456	4578	4701	4824
	UCL	4192	4562	4874	5157	5420	5670	5910	6142	6367	6586	6801
	LCL	3000	2876	2809	2772	2754	2750	2756	2769	2790	2816	2847
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	1696	1785	1875	1965	2055	2144	2234	2324	2414	2503	2593
	UCL	2022	2246	2440	2617	2784	2943	3097	3246	3392	3534	3674
	LCL	1370	1324	1311	1313	1326	1346	1372	1402	1436	1472	1512
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	826	867	907	948	988	1029	1069	1110	1150	1191	1231
	UCL	946	987	1029	1070	1111	1152	1193	1234	1275	1316	1357
	LCL	706	746	786	826	866	906	946	986	1026	1066	1105

Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	1007	1053	1100	1147	1193	1240	1286	1333	1380	1426	1473
	UCL	1143	1246	1336	1419	1498	1574	1647	1718	1788	1857	1925
	LCL	870	861	864	874	889	906	926	948	971	996	1021
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	24289	25474	26658	27842	29027	30211	31395	32580	33764	34948	36133
	UCL	25344	26555	27766	28976	30185	31395	32603	33811	35019	36226	37433
	LCL	23235	24392	25550	26709	27868	29027	30187	31348	32509	33671	34833
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	11310	11953	12595	13238	13881	14524	15166	15809	16452	17095	17737
	UCL	12232	12891	13550	14208	14866	15524	16181	16839	17496	18153	18810
	LCL	10387	11014	11641	12268	12896	13523	14151	14780	15408	16036	16665
Arges-Model_34	Forecast	3628	3855	4083	4310	4538	4765	4992	5220	5447	5674	5902
	UCL	3936	4169	4402	4635	4868	5101	5333	5566	5798	6031	6263
	LCL	3320	3541	3763	3985	4207	4429	4651	4873	5096	5318	5541
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	838	887	935	984	1032	1081	1130	1178	1227	1275	1324
	UCL	932	981	1030	1079	1128	1177	1226	1275	1324	1373	1423
	LCL	744	792	840	889	937	985	1033	1081	1129	1177	1225
Dâmbovita- Model_36	Forecast	1904	2015	2127	2238	2350	2461	2573	2684	2796	2907	3019
	UCL	2057	2169	2282	2394	2506	2618	2731	2843	2955	3067	3180
	LCL	1750	1861	1972	2083	2193	2304	2415	2526	2636	2747	2858
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	853	918	983	1048	1113	1178	1243	1308	1373	1438	1503
	UCL	934	1049	1171	1300	1435	1576	1721	1872	2027	2186	2350
	LCL	773	788	795	796	791	780	764	744	719	689	655
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	749	788	827	865	904	943	981	1020	1059	1097	1136
	UCL	819	858	897	936	975	1014	1053	1092	1131	1170	1209
	LCL	680	718	756	795	833	871	910	948	987	1025	1063
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	2588	2724	2861	2998	3134	3271	3407	3544	3681	3817	3954
	UCL	2960	3251	3506	3742	3967	4183	4393	4597	4798	4995	5189
	LCL	2215	2198	2216	2253	2302	2359	2422	2491	2564	2640	2719

Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	721	760	800	840	879	919	958	998	1038	1077	1117
	UCL	824	906	979	1046	1110	1172	1232	1290	1348	1404	1460
	LCL	617	614	621	633	648	666	685	706	728	751	774
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	13560	14279	14998	15717	16436	17155	17874	18593	19313	20032	20751
	UCL	15135	15883	16630	17377	18124	18870	19616	20361	21106	21851	22595
	LCL	11985	12675	13366	14057	14749	15441	16133	16826	17519	18212	18906
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	10652	11193	11733	12273	12814	13354	13894	14435	14975	15515	16056
	UCL	12163	12731	13299	13867	14434	15000	15567	16132	16698	17263	17828
	LCL	9142	9654	10167	10680	11194	11708	12222	12737	13252	13768	14284
Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	2895	3055	3216	3377	3537	3698	3858	4019	4180	4340	4501
	UCL	3168	3441	3689	3923	4148	4367	4581	4792	4999	5204	5407
	LCL	2622	2669	2743	2830	2927	3029	3136	3247	3360	3477	3595
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	15379	16053	16726	17400	18073	18747	19421	20094	20768	21442	22115
	UCL	15846	16538	17230	17921	18611	19301	19991	20680	21368	22057	22744
	LCL	14912	15567	16223	16879	17536	18193	18851	19509	20168	20827	21486
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	6898	7256	7613	7971	8328	8686	9043	9401	9758	10116	10473
	UCL	7636	8299	8891	9447	9978	10493	10995	11488	11972	12449	12920
	LCL	6161	6212	6335	6495	6678	6878	7091	7314	7544	7782	8026
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	1957	2067	2176	2286	2395	2505	2614	2724	2833	2943	3052
	UCL	2222	2441	2634	2814	2986	3152	3314	3471	3626	3778	3929
	LCL	1693	1693	1719	1757	1804	1857	1915	1976	2040	2107	2175
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	1172	1228	1283	1338	1393	1449	1504	1559	1614	1670	1725
	UCL	1257	1347	1429	1507	1583	1656	1728	1798	1868	1937	2006
	LCL	1088	1108	1136	1169	1204	1241	1280	1320	1361	1402	1444
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	899	941	982	1024	1065	1107	1148	1190	1231	1273	1314
	UCL	1000	1083	1156	1225	1290	1353	1414	1474	1532	1590	1647
	LCL	799	799	808	823	841	861	882	906	930	955	981

Olt-Model_49	Forecast	1102	1172	1243	1314	1385	1456	1527	1597	1668	1739	1810
	UCL	1221	1294	1367	1440	1513	1586	1659	1732	1805	1878	1950
	LCL	982	1050	1119	1188	1256	1325	1394	1463	1532	1601	1669
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1795	1879	1964	2049	2133	2218	2302	2387	2472	2556	2641
	UCL	1994	2161	2309	2447	2579	2706	2829	2950	3069	3186	3302
	LCL	1595	1598	1619	1650	1688	1730	1776	1824	1874	1927	1980
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	8890	9365	9839	10314	10789	11264	11738	12213	12688	13163	13637
	UCL	10073	10569	11066	11562	12057	12553	13048	13542	14037	14531	15025
	LCL	7707	8160	8613	9067	9520	9975	10429	10884	11339	11794	12250
Arad-Model_52	Forecast	2263	2373	2484	2594	2704	2815	2925	3035	3146	3256	3366
	UCL	2477	2589	2702	2814	2926	3038	3150	3262	3374	3486	3598
	LCL	2049	2157	2266	2374	2483	2591	2700	2809	2917	3026	3134
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	906	947	987	1027	1067	1108	1148	1188	1228	1268	1309
	UCL	1043	1084	1125	1166	1207	1248	1289	1330	1371	1412	1453
	LCL	769	809	848	888	927	967	1006	1046	1085	1125	1165
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	1724	1818	1911	2004	2097	2191	2284	2377	2470	2563	2657
	UCL	1942	2039	2136	2233	2331	2428	2525	2622	2719	2815	2912
	LCL	1507	1596	1686	1775	1864	1953	2043	2132	2222	2311	2401
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	3749	3957	4164	4372	4579	4787	4994	5202	5409	5617	5824
	UCL	4520	5047	5499	5913	6303	6675	7033	7381	7721	8054	8380
	LCL	2979	2867	2830	2830	2856	2899	2955	3022	3097	3179	3268

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: Journal of Education Studies (JES). Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University

European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>.

(Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)

EXPLORING SECTOR-SPECIFIC ADVANCEMENTS IN ACCOMMODATION AND FOOD SERVICE ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION FROM 2008 TO 2018: AN ACADEMIC INQUIRY

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Abstract:

This academic inquiry delves into the intricate dynamics of the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sector within the Romanian Mountainous Region over the period spanning 2008 to 2018. The study employs a rigorous analytical approach, combining statistical analysis and parametric testing methodologies to unravel the sector's nuanced developments.

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Introduction:

The Romanian Mountainous Region presents a unique backdrop for investigating the sector-specific advancements in Accommodation and Food Service Activities. This comprehensive analysis aims to unravel the underlying trends and influences that have shaped the industry landscape over the specified temporal scope.

Methodology:

The research methodology integrates statistical figures (panels a-f) and annex Parametric Analysis Romania to establish a foundation for robust analysis. Key statistical indicators, such as mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and percentiles, are meticulously examined to capture the sector's multifaceted characteristics.

Statistical Insights:

The statistical data reveals ascending trends in both mean and median values for Accommodation and Food Service Activities. While maintaining a central symmetry, the distribution curves exhibit concentrated scores around

the mean, portraying leptokurtosis with unimodal characteristics. Antagonistic fluctuations in certain indicators highlight the complexity of the sector's evolution.

Working Assumptions:

The study assumes a normal distribution of scores, necessitating the application of parametric tests. Logarithmization of obtained values aligns the distribution with the Gauss-Laplace normal curve, providing a balanced perspective on the sector's dynamics.

Results:

The statistical data pertaining to the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sectors (figures 2.6.1 – 2.6.5 and chapter 2 annexes) reveals an upward trajectory in both average and median values for each sector. However, other statistical indicators exhibit occasional contradictory fluctuations (including Average, Std. Error of the Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentile 50 Value). The specific values are as follows: a mean of 65,417.89, a standard error of the mean at 3,315.506, a median of 64,404.00,

a standard deviation of 9,946.518, a variance of 98,933,224.611, Skewness of -0.009, a standard error of Skewness at 0.717, Kurtosis at -1.223, a standard error of Kurtosis at 1.400, a distance of 28,301, a minimum value of 51,206, and a maximum value of 79,507. The 25th percentile is 56,555.504, and the 75th percentile is 74,913.00.

These presented values signify positive growth and development within the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sectors in the mountainous region of Romania. Despite occasional sectors exhibiting negative values, the overall business situation in the mountainous area appears favorable.

The central tendency analysis of the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sectors over the analyzed period indicates substantial growth in the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2019. The statistical data associated with this indicator demonstrates a high level of consistency, signifying positive results with minimal deviation. Symmetrical distributions suggest a stabilizing business environment during the analyzed period. Additionally, the low standard error of Kurtosis implies increased concentration within certain industries.

Figure 2.6.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

The predictive analysis for the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the mountainous region of Romania suggests sustained growth until 2030 (table 1). At the national, macro-regional, regional, and county levels, statistical models reveal varying levels of sustainability across different mountainous areas. The harmonization statistics feature significant values for the mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in the following order):

- Stationary R-squared: 0.581, 0.345, -1.110E-15, 0.902, -4,441E-16, 0.000
- R-square: 0.922, 0.060, 0.673, 1.000, 0.811, 0.847
- RMSE: 202,407, 228,034, 0.000, 980,739, 34,002, 40,898
- MAPS: 5,888, 2,565, 0.000, 12,517, 1,050, 1,649
- MaxAPE: 23,673, 10,336, 0.000, 47,986, 2,657, 4,745
- MAE: 135,854, 158,860, 0.000, 707,587, 22,772, 26,172
- MaxAE: 429,131, 467,324, 0.000, 1,832,895, 74,976, 87,132
- Normalized BIC: 10,029, 1,954, 7,293, 14,265, 7,474, 7,869

These statistical measures offer valuable insights into the sustainability and growth potential of the various sectors at different geographical levels, providing a comprehensive understanding of the economic landscape in the mountainous regions of Romania.

Analysis and Implications:

The analysis rejects the null hypothesis after logarithmization, paving the way for a nuanced exploration of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses, considering normal limits, facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the sector's evolution. The central tendency indicates a noteworthy increase in active enterprises within the Romanian Mountainous Region, even as the growth rate experiences fluctuations.

Conclusion:

This academic inquiry offers valuable insights into the sector-specific advancements in Accommodation and Food Service Activities within the Romanian Mountainous Region. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the industry's trajectory, providing a foundation for future research and strategic decision-making within the economic landscape.

Table 1. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S6

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	83503	87123	90743	94364	97984	10160	10522	10884	11246	11608	11970
	UCL	85822	89525	93226	96925	10062	10431	10800	11169	11538	11907	12275
	LCL	81183	84720	88260	91802	95347	98894	10244	10599	10954	11309	11665
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	24452	25433	26414	27395	28376	29357	30338	31320	32301	33282	34263
	UCL	24868	25866	26863	27860	28856	29851	30847	31842	32836	33830	34824
	LCL	24035	25000	25965	26930	27897	28863	29830	30798	31765	32734	33702
Nord-Vest- Model_3	Forecast	15607	16385	17163	17941	18719	19497	20274	21052	21830	22608	23386
	UCL	17412	18224	19036	19847	20657	21467	22276	23085	23893	24701	25508
	LCL	13801	14545	15290	16035	16780	17527	18273	19020	19768	20516	21264
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	3641	3810	3978	4147	4316	4484	4653	4822	4990	5159	5328

	UCL	3880	4052	4224	4396	4568	4740	4912	5084	5256	5428	5600
	LCL	3402	3567	3732	3898	4063	4228	4394	4559	4724	4890	5055
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	1338	1416	1494	1571	1649	1727	1804	1882	1960	2038	2115
	UCL	1445	1524	1604	1683	1763	1842	1921	2001	2080	2160	2239
	LCL	1232	1308	1383	1459	1535	1611	1687	1763	1839	1916	1992
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	5837	6148	6458	6768	7078	7389	7699	8009	8319	8630	8940
	UCL	7179	8045	8781	9451	10078	10675	11248	11803	12344	12872	13389
	LCL	4496	4250	4134	4085	4079	4103	4150	4215	4295	4388	4491
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	1869	1881	1893	1905	1917	1929	1941	1952	1964	1976	1988
	UCL	2068	2259	2482	2732	3008	3307	3627	3966	4325	4701	5095
	LCL	1670	1503	1304	1077	825	551	254	-62	-396	-749	-1119
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	1329	1386	1443	1501	1558	1616	1673	1730	1788	1845	1902
	UCL	1503	1563	1623	1684	1744	1804	1865	1925	1985	2045	2105
	LCL	1155	1209	1263	1318	1372	1427	1481	1536	1590	1645	1700
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1107	1155	1204	1252	1300	1349	1397	1445	1494	1542	1590
	UCL	1219	1270	1320	1371	1421	1471	1522	1572	1622	1672	1723
	LCL	994	1040	1087	1133	1179	1226	1272	1319	1365	1412	1458
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	9617	10067	10517	10968	11418	11868	12318	12768	13219	13669	14119
	UCL	10620	11075	11531	11987	12442	12898	13353	13809	14264	14720	15175
	LCL	8614	9059	9504	9948	10393	10838	11283	11728	12173	12618	13063
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	1506	1576	1647	1717	1787	1857	1927	1997	2067	2137	2207
	UCL	1606	1677	1749	1820	1892	1963	2035	2106	2177	2249	2320
	LCL	1407	1476	1544	1613	1682	1750	1819	1888	1957	2025	2094
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	2547	2671	2795	2919	3043	3167	3291	3415	3539	3663	3787
	UCL	2811	2937	3062	3187	3312	3438	3563	3688	3814	3939	4064
	LCL	2283	2406	2528	2651	2774	2896	3019	3142	3264	3387	3510

Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	659	687	715	743	772	800	828	857	885	913	941
	UCL	762	791	820	849	878	906	935	964	993	1021	1050
	LCL	555	583	610	638	666	694	721	749	777	805	833
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	807	840	872	904	937	969	1001	1034	1066	1098	1131
	UCL	906	938	971	1004	1037	1070	1103	1135	1168	1201	1234
	LCL	709	741	773	804	836	868	900	932	964	996	1028
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	2108	2212	2316	2420	2524	2628	2732	2836	2940	3044	3148
	UCL	2321	2426	2531	2636	2741	2847	2952	3057	3162	3267	3373
	LCL	1895	1997	2100	2203	2306	2409	2511	2614	2717	2820	2923
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	1998	2090	2181	2273	2364	2456	2547	2639	2730	2822	2913
	UCL	2258	2355	2451	2547	2644	2740	2836	2932	3028	3123	3219
	LCL	1738	1824	1911	1998	2085	2172	2259	2346	2433	2520	2608
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	19375	20157	20938	21719	22500	23282	24063	24844	25625	26407	27188
	UCL	19916	20712	21507	22303	23098	23892	24687	25481	26275	27068	27862
	LCL	18835	19601	20368	21135	21903	22671	23439	24208	24976	25745	26514
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	9883	10438	10994	11549	12105	12660	13216	13771	14326	14882	15437
	UCL	11012	11588	12163	12739	13314	13889	14463	15038	15611	16185	16759
	LCL	8754	9289	9824	10359	10895	11431	11968	12504	13041	13578	14116
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	2130	2252	2375	2497	2619	2742	2864	2987	3109	3231	3354
	UCL	2424	2552	2680	2807	2935	3062	3190	3317	3444	3571	3699
	LCL	1836	1953	2070	2187	2304	2421	2539	2656	2774	2891	3009
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	803	849	894	939	985	1030	1076	1121	1167	1212	1257
	UCL	962	1008	1054	1100	1147	1193	1239	1285	1332	1378	1424
	LCL	645	689	734	778	823	868	912	957	1001	1046	1091
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2446	2594	2743	2891	3040	3188	3337	3485	3634	3782	3931
	UCL	2854	3011	3167	3323	3479	3634	3790	3945	4101	4256	4411
	LCL	2037	2178	2319	2460	2601	2742	2884	3025	3167	3308	3450

Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1351	1416	1482	1548	1613	1679	1744	1810	1876	1941	2007
	UCL	1481	1547	1613	1680	1746	1812	1878	1945	2011	2077	2144
	LCL	1221	1286	1351	1416	1481	1545	1610	1675	1740	1805	1870
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	2331	2460	2589	2718	2848	2977	3106	3235	3364	3493	3622
	UCL	2500	2631	2762	2894	3025	3156	3288	3419	3550	3681	3812
	LCL	2162	2289	2416	2543	2670	2797	2924	3051	3178	3305	3432
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	814	859	903	948	992	1037	1081	1126	1170	1214	1259
	UCL	891	937	983	1028	1074	1119	1165	1211	1256	1302	1347
	LCL	738	781	824	867	911	954	997	1040	1084	1127	1170
Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	10289	10758	11226	11694	12163	12631	13099	13568	14036	14505	14973
	UCL	11660	12155	12649	13143	13637	14130	14623	15115	15607	16099	16590
	LCL	8919	9361	9803	10246	10689	11132	11576	12021	12465	12911	13356
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	1419	1507	1595	1683	1771	1859	1947	2035	2123	2211	2299
	UCL	1587	1676	1765	1854	1943	2032	2121	2210	2299	2388	2476
	LCL	1251	1338	1425	1512	1600	1687	1774	1861	1948	2035	2122
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	1440	1502	1564	1625	1687	1749	1811	1872	1934	1996	2057
	UCL	1581	1645	1709	1773	1838	1902	1966	2030	2094	2158	2222
	LCL	1300	1359	1418	1478	1537	1596	1655	1715	1774	1833	1893
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	3596	3719	3841	3964	4087	4210	4333	4456	4578	4701	4824
	UCL	4192	4562	4874	5157	5420	5670	5910	6142	6367	6586	6801
	LCL	3000	2876	2809	2772	2754	2750	2756	2769	2790	2816	2847
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	1696	1785	1875	1965	2055	2144	2234	2324	2414	2503	2593
	UCL	2022	2246	2440	2617	2784	2943	3097	3246	3392	3534	3674
	LCL	1370	1324	1311	1313	1326	1346	1372	1402	1436	1472	1512
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	826	867	907	948	988	1029	1069	1110	1150	1191	1231
	UCL	946	987	1029	1070	1111	1152	1193	1234	1275	1316	1357
	LCL	706	746	786	826	866	906	946	986	1026	1066	1105

Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	1007	1053	1100	1147	1193	1240	1286	1333	1380	1426	1473
	UCL	1143	1246	1336	1419	1498	1574	1647	1718	1788	1857	1925
	LCL	870	861	864	874	889	906	926	948	971	996	1021
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	24289	25474	26658	27842	29027	30211	31395	32580	33764	34948	36133
	UCL	25344	26555	27766	28976	30185	31395	32603	33811	35019	36226	37433
	LCL	23235	24392	25550	26709	27868	29027	30187	31348	32509	33671	34833
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	11310	11953	12595	13238	13881	14524	15166	15809	16452	17095	17737
	UCL	12232	12891	13550	14208	14866	15524	16181	16839	17496	18153	18810
	LCL	10387	11014	11641	12268	12896	13523	14151	14780	15408	16036	16665
Arges-Model_34	Forecast	3628	3855	4083	4310	4538	4765	4992	5220	5447	5674	5902
	UCL	3936	4169	4402	4635	4868	5101	5333	5566	5798	6031	6263
	LCL	3320	3541	3763	3985	4207	4429	4651	4873	5096	5318	5541
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	838	887	935	984	1032	1081	1130	1178	1227	1275	1324
	UCL	932	981	1030	1079	1128	1177	1226	1275	1324	1373	1423
	LCL	744	792	840	889	937	985	1033	1081	1129	1177	1225
Dâmbovita- Model_36	Forecast	1904	2015	2127	2238	2350	2461	2573	2684	2796	2907	3019
	UCL	2057	2169	2282	2394	2506	2618	2731	2843	2955	3067	3180
	LCL	1750	1861	1972	2083	2193	2304	2415	2526	2636	2747	2858
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	853	918	983	1048	1113	1178	1243	1308	1373	1438	1503
	UCL	934	1049	1171	1300	1435	1576	1721	1872	2027	2186	2350
	LCL	773	788	795	796	791	780	764	744	719	689	655
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	749	788	827	865	904	943	981	1020	1059	1097	1136
	UCL	819	858	897	936	975	1014	1053	1092	1131	1170	1209
	LCL	680	718	756	795	833	871	910	948	987	1025	1063
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	2588	2724	2861	2998	3134	3271	3407	3544	3681	3817	3954
	UCL	2960	3251	3506	3742	3967	4183	4393	4597	4798	4995	5189
	LCL	2215	2198	2216	2253	2302	2359	2422	2491	2564	2640	2719

Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	721	760	800	840	879	919	958	998	1038	1077	1117
	UCL	824	906	979	1046	1110	1172	1232	1290	1348	1404	1460
	LCL	617	614	621	633	648	666	685	706	728	751	774
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	13560	14279	14998	15717	16436	17155	17874	18593	19313	20032	20751
	UCL	15135	15883	16630	17377	18124	18870	19616	20361	21106	21851	22595
	LCL	11985	12675	13366	14057	14749	15441	16133	16826	17519	18212	18906
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	10652	11193	11733	12273	12814	13354	13894	14435	14975	15515	16056
	UCL	12163	12731	13299	13867	14434	15000	15567	16132	16698	17263	17828
	LCL	9142	9654	10167	10680	11194	11708	12222	12737	13252	13768	14284
Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	2895	3055	3216	3377	3537	3698	3858	4019	4180	4340	4501
	UCL	3168	3441	3689	3923	4148	4367	4581	4792	4999	5204	5407
	LCL	2622	2669	2743	2830	2927	3029	3136	3247	3360	3477	3595
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	15379	16053	16726	17400	18073	18747	19421	20094	20768	21442	22115
	UCL	15846	16538	17230	17921	18611	19301	19991	20680	21368	22057	22744
	LCL	14912	15567	16223	16879	17536	18193	18851	19509	20168	20827	21486
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	6898	7256	7613	7971	8328	8686	9043	9401	9758	10116	10473
	UCL	7636	8299	8891	9447	9978	10493	10995	11488	11972	12449	12920
	LCL	6161	6212	6335	6495	6678	6878	7091	7314	7544	7782	8026
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	1957	2067	2176	2286	2395	2505	2614	2724	2833	2943	3052
	UCL	2222	2441	2634	2814	2986	3152	3314	3471	3626	3778	3929
	LCL	1693	1693	1719	1757	1804	1857	1915	1976	2040	2107	2175
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	1172	1228	1283	1338	1393	1449	1504	1559	1614	1670	1725
	UCL	1257	1347	1429	1507	1583	1656	1728	1798	1868	1937	2006
	LCL	1088	1108	1136	1169	1204	1241	1280	1320	1361	1402	1444
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	899	941	982	1024	1065	1107	1148	1190	1231	1273	1314
	UCL	1000	1083	1156	1225	1290	1353	1414	1474	1532	1590	1647
	LCL	799	799	808	823	841	861	882	906	930	955	981

Olt-Model_49	Forecast	1102	1172	1243	1314	1385	1456	1527	1597	1668	1739	1810
	UCL	1221	1294	1367	1440	1513	1586	1659	1732	1805	1878	1950
	LCL	982	1050	1119	1188	1256	1325	1394	1463	1532	1601	1669
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1795	1879	1964	2049	2133	2218	2302	2387	2472	2556	2641
	UCL	1994	2161	2309	2447	2579	2706	2829	2950	3069	3186	3302
	LCL	1595	1598	1619	1650	1688	1730	1776	1824	1874	1927	1980
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	8890	9365	9839	10314	10789	11264	11738	12213	12688	13163	13637
	UCL	10073	10569	11066	11562	12057	12553	13048	13542	14037	14531	15025
	LCL	7707	8160	8613	9067	9520	9975	10429	10884	11339	11794	12250
Arad-Model_52	Forecast	2263	2373	2484	2594	2704	2815	2925	3035	3146	3256	3366
	UCL	2477	2589	2702	2814	2926	3038	3150	3262	3374	3486	3598
	LCL	2049	2157	2266	2374	2483	2591	2700	2809	2917	3026	3134
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	906	947	987	1027	1067	1108	1148	1188	1228	1268	1309
	UCL	1043	1084	1125	1166	1207	1248	1289	1330	1371	1412	1453
	LCL	769	809	848	888	927	967	1006	1046	1085	1125	1165
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	1724	1818	1911	2004	2097	2191	2284	2377	2470	2563	2657
	UCL	1942	2039	2136	2233	2331	2428	2525	2622	2719	2815	2912
	LCL	1507	1596	1686	1775	1864	1953	2043	2132	2222	2311	2401
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	3749	3957	4164	4372	4579	4787	4994	5202	5409	5617	5824
	UCL	4520	5047	5499	5913	6303	6675	7033	7381	7721	8054	8380
	LCL	2979	2867	2830	2830	2856	2899	2955	3022	3097	3179	3268

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University

European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)